

Ethnomedicinal and Economic Importance Of Some Plants of Euphorbiaceae Family at Chhatarpur District (M.P.)

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Abstract

Family Euphorbiaceae is one of the largest family of Angiosperm composed of 300 genera and 8000 species and about 195 species are found in India. Present paper highlights the ethnomedicinal significance and economic importance of this family Euphorbiaceae at Chhatarpur district (M.P. India). The objectives to document the Euphorbiaceae species traditionally used by tribal or local communities particularly traditional healers, herbal practitioners and gatherers, to record medicinal plant parts, formulations and medicinal importance. Finding revealed that several Euphorbiaceae family members like *Euphorbia hirta*, *Ricinus communis*, *Jatropha gossypifolia*, *Jatropha integerrima*, *Jatropha podagrica*, *E. thymifolia*, *E. pulcherrima*, *E. dentata*, *E. tirucalli*, *E. microphylla*, *E. lophogona*, *E. nerifolia* etc occurring in the dry deciduous condition as present in Chhatarpur district, this study has been done during 2023 to 2025 August. The phytochemical speciality latex and milk are useful in treating many skin, inflammation, arthritis, muscular pain, respiratory problems and wound healings. The latex, leaves, seeds, and roots, were the most frequently utilized parts with external applications (pastes, poultices, fumigant, oil, leaf decoction) and simple decoctions being common methods of preparation. The study emphasizes the importance of conserving indigenous knowledge promoting sustainable harvesting.

Keywords

Euphorbiaceae, Chhatarpur, Ethnobotany, Traditional Medicine.

Introduction

The family Euphorbiaceae is one of the largest family of tropical dry deciduous climatic condition comprising over 300 genera and 8000 species approximately. The members of this family have different habitats like herb, shrub, trees, and climbers with erect and prostrate branching due to presence of latex and milky substance this family is important to cure many health issues, like rheumatism, inflammation, skin cure, respiratory problem, muscular problems and wounds.

Objective of study

The objectives to document the Euphorbiaceae species traditionally used by tribal or local communities particularly traditional healers, herbal practitioners and gatherers, to record medicinal plant parts, formulations and medicinal importance.

Review of Literature

There has been some work done in the field of pharmacology by many workers like Jain et al., (1994), Seigler et al., (1994), and Yu, C.X. et al., (2020) the presence of secondary metabolites such as flavonoids, terpenoids, alkaloids, tannins, phenolics and saponins Seigler et al., (1994) which possess antimicrobial, antioxidant, analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties in different plant parts of family Euphorbiaceae members. During study period some interview has been done on different four study sites Nowgong, Bijawar, Maharajpur, and Kishangarh and with Vaidya's Ayurveda, old experienced lady during history period history of disease and, knowledge, causes, symptoms, route of medicine asked by peoples at each interview have been taken with different age group-persons. These findings are consistent with earlier reports such as *Euphorbia hirta*, *Euphorbia geniculata*, *Ricinus communis*, *Jatropha curcus*, and *Phyllanthus emblica* are widely used by the people of this district for folk medicines. The predominance of leaves and oil (common) *Euphorbia hirta* (Whole plant extract) and roots as the most frequently used plant parts suggests a long standing recognition of their therapeutic potency.

Main Text

The application methods, mainly decoctions, pastes, poultices and oil also reflect simple yet effective techniques that have been sustained across generations such practices are not only cost effective but also accessible, which explains the continued relevance in rural and tribal healthcare as Chhatarpur district. However it is also important to know certain limitations the ethnomedicinal knowledge documented is largely based on oral traditions, which are vulnerable to loss due to changing sociocultural dynamics.

List of recorded species of Euphorbiaceae family and their medicinal use and economic importance.

S. No	Botanical Name	Local Name	Habit	Part used	Medicinal uses	Route of medicine	Economic importance
1	Ricinus communis	Arandi	shrub	Root Leaf Seed	Root is used to fertility Leaf is used to lactation Seed is used to labour induction	Root + Honey	Agriculture uses, medicinal uses, Industrial uses
2	Jatropha Curcus	Ratanjot	shrub	Root Leaf	Root is used to stomach pain Leaf is used to anti-inflammatory	Leaf +Oil	Medicinal uses, cosmetic industry, Food industry
3	Phyllanthus emblica	Amla	Tree	Leaf Fruit	Leaf is used to digestive health, diabetes, Respiratory disorder. Fruit is used to urinary health	Seed + Honey	Food industry (Murabba), Cosmetic industry (Hear Oils, Shampoos)
4	Euphorbia thymifolia	Choti Dudhi	Herb	Latex	Latex is used to Anti-Inflammatory, skin problems	Latex + Ghee	Medicinal Industries(Diarrhea, Skin diseases) Veterinary uses.
5	Euphorbia-hirta	Dudhi	Herb	Leaf	Leaf is used to medicinal importance, Inflammation	Whole plant + Honey	Medicinal Importance (Urinary disorder)
6	Euphorbia geniculata	Dudhi	Herb	Latex	Latex is used to skin disease	Latex+Honey	Respiratory Problems, stomach pain, wound healing.S
7	Phyllanthus niruri	Bhum i Amla	Herb	Root	Root is used to Viral Hepatitis	Stem + Honey	Medicinal uses (Liver disorder, diabetes, digestive problem, urinary problem, skin diseases)

Ricinus communis, Jatropha curcus, Phyllanthus emblica, Euphorbia hirta.

Conclusion

The present study demonstrates that members of the family Euphorbiaceae occupy an important place in the traditional healthcare practices of Chhatarpur district, Local communities make extensive use of species from this family for the treatment of skin

infection, digestive disorder, piles eye problem, inflammation, respiratory nerve problems and wound and healings. The predominance of latex, leaves, fruit (*Emblca officinalis* is rich source of vitamin-c and calcium) and roots as medicinal parts reflects the deep traditional knowledge of their therapeutic value. In the last findings emphasize the need for systematic conservation of indigenous knowledge, sustainable harvesting process.

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